

Running Head: DLT for 5G

The potential use of DLT to make 5G networks more flexible and adaptable to improve coverage.

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Abstract:

This paper proposes a new concept for making 5G networks flexible and adaptable. It introduces an approach and the method to execute it which can help attain maximum coverage, both in terms of efficiency and area, by allowing the eNodeBs/small cells to adjust their range according to the load and requirements of the network.

The concept proposed in this paper also introduces a new potential dimension to the spider graph used by most companies and organizations involved in the development of 5G technologies and networks for comparing the performances of wireless technologies used for communication, which directly or indirectly affects the existing dimensions.

The concept incorporates DLT, the abbreviation for Distributed Ledger Technology, and its approach towards data, i.e. decentralization to achieve streamlined processing and security. The ideas and technologies are carefully put together to attain the objective of enhancing the overall QoS.

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1.1 Introduction

5G is revolutionary, and this is unanimous. But like every revolution, it brings challenges alongside. We are left with nothing but the option to catch up with the requirements of 5G in order to bring it to life and benefit from it. There are many technologies coming together in this effort to make 5G possible. Focused efforts, around the globe are being made by the leaders of technology.

5G focuses on many things, such as **throughput, latency, customer experience, power consumption, coverage**, etc.

I'd like to make a contribution to the latter mentioned point, the **coverage**. Coverage is one of the most noticed by the consumers, and plays a very significant role in determining whether a network is efficient or not. A great customer experience is driven largely by the fact that, how robust is the coverage of a network, irrespective of the location of the customer and the load on the network.

This persuades us to address this aspect of network connectivity seriously, and making sincere efforts to make every network, be it 2G, 3G, 4G or the prodigal son of networking 5G a better version of itself.

1.2 Proposed action

As known, the mobile networks we use are cellular, i.e. the area of coverage under one **eNodeB/small cell**. The coverage areas are however static. That constricts the adaptability of the network. This problem can be answered if **DLT (Distributed Ledger Technology)** is introduced for the **eNodeBs/small cells** to have decentralized ledgers. The ledgers which each eNodeB would have, shall contain the location of every other eNodeB on the network. The **eNodeBs/small cells** would then smartly assess the coverage under the other eNodeBs. If one is overloaded, it can place a request for load-sharing to the DLT network. And when the participating **eNodeBs/small cells** on the network can reach to a consensus, the power transmitted by the former eNodeB/small cell and the helping eNodeB would be adjusted accordingly.

The consensus that the DLT network would have to reach would be around the below major points:

- **Has the requesting node reached the critical value of it's capacity?**
- **Are the closest eNodeBs/small cells already facing extreme loads? Y/N?**
- **Are the closest eNodeBs/small cells already sharing loads with other eNodeBs/small cells? Y/N?**

If the request placed by the former **eNodeB/small cell** which asks for load-sharing gets positive responses for the above mentioned parameters, the request would be validated and the **eNodeBs/small cell** would adjust the power they're transmitting towards each others directions.

The installation of a new **eNodeB/small cell** would be updated with its location and serving capacity to the DLT network and it would instantly become a participating member.

1.3 Overview of DLT:

1.3.1 Introduction: DLT is the abbreviation for Distributed Ledger Technology. It is centered around the concept of decentralizing, primarily data. It has a variety of groundbreaking techniques for maintaining the quality of data and ensuring its security. The DLT contains a digital ledger which holds the records of every valid transaction of data. This ledger is distributed across all the participating nodes of the network. A node is every participant on the network who means to send and receive transactions. The ledger is updated whenever a new transaction is validated and this update is made uniformly throughout every copy of the ledger which, as already mentioned, is distributed amongst all the nodes.

The update is made real-time, so there is no ledger lagging. Every transaction depends on the consensus between all the nodes on the network to get validated. The transactions can be anything varying monetary assets to digital tokens, property assets, etc.

1.3.2 Security: The security of transmission of assets and their data in DLT is ensured mainly by the use of hash functions. The characteristic of the

hash function which makes it infeasible to compromise with its security is that, it is untraceable.

That would mean, that once a message is processed by a hash function, it gets converted into a message digest. This digest cannot be used to trace back to the original data by decoding it. One major reason for such irreversibility is that the length of the output of the hash function is independent of the input message.

1.3.3 Reliability: The data on the ledger in DLT is immutable, which makes it highly reliable. Immutability of data refers to its property of being unchangeable. The foundational concept of creating a consensus between distinct parties lying at different nodes on the network, is the major reason behind ensuring the immutability of data in DLT. Due to this, it is not possible to make any malicious changes to the data. If a node on the network is compromised, and tries to make malicious changes to the ledger, the network won't reach a consensus and hence, the ledger remains secure.

1.4 Cases of operation

Case 1	Case 2
<p>This demonstrates a UE lying under the coverage of eNodeB_1, and availing network services from eNodeB_1 under normal load conditions. The eNodeB would provide the services offered by the network provider without any anomalies.</p> <p>eNodeB_1 UE eNodeB_2</p>	

1.5 Process of transition:

Every eNodeB/small cell acts as a node on the network. When a node, let's assume eNodeB_1 faces high network traffic or extreme loads, it pushes a token for consensus by the network, which would, as mentioned already have all other eNodeBs connected. The network then analyzes the following conditions:

- Has the requesting node reached the critical value of it's capacity?
- Are the closest eNodeBs/small cells already facing extreme loads?
Y/N?
- Are the closest eNodeBs/small cells already sharing loads with other eNodeBs/small cells? Y/N?

After these conditions are analyzed and the responses for both the questions comes back a **N**, which is a positive response from the perspective of the node pushing the request, the closest eNodeB initiates the process of load-sharing. It is executed when the power radiated by eNodeB_1 in a particular direction is dynamically reduced and the helping node increases the power it radiates the same direction as eNodeB.

1.6 What would the ledgers hold?

A different set of distributed ledgers linked and belonging individually to every eNodeB/small cell would hold the data regarding the location coordinates of all the eNodeBs/small cells on the network, and the maximum number of customers that an eNodeB/small cell can serve, and the number of customers they are serving in real time, which keep updating in real-time as well.

Another set of distributed ledgers would hold the number of total requests pushed by every node, whether validated or not.

The primary ledger would host the requests that are pushed by any node on the number, which need consensus for validation, and also once they're validated. The request which fail to get validated won't be a part of storage of the primary ledger.

1.7 Flowchart

A **graphical representation** of a possible flowchart for the sequence of the entire process follows:

1.8 A New Dimension

This approach simultaneously looks to add a new dimension to our perspective towards 5G through the multi-dimensional spider graph used to compare the services of the various generations of wireless communication. Along with the various parameters already being considered, a new parameter that this article and this approach proposes is **network adaptability/flexibility**.

This network parameter directly or indirectly relates to almost all the other parameters, such as the latency, customer experience, power consumption, etc. as this ensures a smart usage of network resources which can affect the overall quality of the network.

Given below is a graphical representation of this new proposed network dimension, which can also immensely affect business approaches. It is marked by the longest bold line.

The unit to measure the performance on this dimension would be the ratio of requests validated to the total requests pushed per second to the network.

1.8 Potential benefits:

There are many possible benefits that such a system can provide, such as:

- **Reduce the Capex:** instead of facing the need to install a large number of eNodeBs/small cells at a very rapid pace to initiate the commercial launch of 5G services to the customers, the services can be initiated with a comparatively lesser number of eNodeBs/small cells with more and more being install as we move ahead in time.
- **The eNodeBs/small cells being aware of themselves and able to share their loads smartly would make the network more dynamic.**
- **A huge amount of data would be generated by the communication of eNodeBs/small cells amongst each other, regarding which ones place the highest number of load-sharing requests, which thereby, would give a deeper and more precise insight into the magnitude and pattern of usage of the 5G services in the respective areas. This might help companies make targeted efforts in specific regions according to the insights that they generate and improve customer experience.**
- **The expedited launch of 5G services which can be made possible, as I already mentioned, can provide a faster RoI to the**

- operators and accelerate the process of further expansion of their networks.
- Security of the communication is indeed a very important factor. This would also be ensured by the DLT as there is no centralized database, it is instead decentralized and every request would need a consensus from the network to be validated and subsequently executed, which would ensure that the communication stays immune to any attacks.
- 6. The scalability of such a system is not limited to 5G, but can also extend to legacy systems as well.
- Efficient consumption of power by the network elements.
- The coverage efficiency of the networks would be increased as there would hardly be voids where there would be no connectivity to the network.